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PROBLEMS OF PROTECTION OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL HERITAGE IN CULTURAL TOURISM

Abstract. Weak control of the tourism sector, which has economic, social and cultural benefits, excessive use of natural resources and wrong choice of location can have negative effects on the environment, such as the destruction of natural areas, historical values and coastal areas. Also, natural areas of life have been turned into modern holiday settlements, endangered summer houses and beaches have been turned into tourist facilities in the growing tourism sector in our country.

Ugly and uncontrolled structures are growing, wildlife is being abused and tours are being organized without recognizing the flora and fauna and without knowing the region's potential due to the lack of national or regional ecotourism thinking. No matter how well-organized and environmentally friendly the tours are, it is a fact that this tourism, which is carried out without a plan, without control and without studying the capacity of the region, will not be ecotourism.

Key words: Natural resources, forest landscape, cultural tourism, tourist facilities, environment.

Introduction. Ecotourism, which has already been implemented to explore the world, has been on the agenda in our country in recent years, but it is considered to be just mountainous tourism (summer tourism). However, ecotourism, which should be considered as a whole, is an activity that includes many physical activities in a wide range of areas, including social and cultural activities. Today, the Ministries of Tourism of many countries value ecotourism under such headings as summer tourism, ornithological tourism

(bird watching), photo safari, running water sports (kayaking), cultivating tourism, botanical tourism (plant research), cycling tours, equestrian nature walks, cave tourism, mountain tourism and nature walks. As it is known, the basic principle in the use of any natural resource is to ensure a balance of protection and use. Ensuring this balance is also important for the tourism sector. The tourism sector is an environment, which is conducive to the beauty of natural creatures, recreation, health, sports, science and entertainment activities.

Today, the goals that are targeted by the World Tourism Organization and accepted by our republic are:

- a) The status of protection of natural and cultural heritage should be developed;
- b) The living standards of the local population in the wild and protected areas, which are one of the main objectives of tourism selection policy implemented by the Ministry, should also be improved;
- c) Better knowledge and respect for nature, local cultures and their diversity should be propagated.

The interpretation of the main material. Although sea-sun-sand tourism attracts more tourists, the tourist profile is changing and tourism is moving away from traditional “destinations” in the modern world. According to research conducted in the world, eco-tourists are in the age group of 35-54, highly educated, people with high-income and interested in nature, culture and gastronomy. 62% of traditional tourists traveled on holiday in international tourism in 2002, while ecotourism travelers were identified as 4 percent. Instead, the share of expenditures is 7 percent in total tourism income. In addition, return of a large part of ecotourism income to the local population and the fact that these people are the poorest part of society (mountain and forest villagers, as well as family groups running boarding houses), it is not difficult to see that this class will benefit economically from this. In addition, part of the income from ecotourism is spent on the protection of natural resources and the preservation of traditional cultures.

The mass development of tourism also threatens the animal world. The increase of the movement of passenger ships near the beaches to improve the service to tourists leads to the littering of recreation areas with oil products waste, etc. Important elements of recreation are fresh air, tranquility of mountain and forest regions and important natural resources. However, the influx of tourists to uninhabited areas en masse, with new

modes of transport, the expansion of the communication network causes these places to lose their original beauty, but also become uninteresting for many travelers. So, excessive attacks on nature to develop tourism do not serve to protect natural resources or improve the recreation of tourists. In this regard, experts' general opinion is that the solution of problems related to protection, raising the general cultural level of tourism, strengthening legislation and security measures, preparing loading norms for each tourist facility from a scientific point of view should go hand in hand [1, p. 94].

Observations show that a place opened for tourism has lost its ancient originality and attractiveness for a maximum of 15 years. One of the proposals in this regard is that the main tour operators in the world, which direct tourism activities, remove these places from their catalogs, claiming that the environment is polluted after using the tourist centers for some time. For this reason, first of all, it is important to make and implement plans in accordance with the balance of use, so that places that are considered to be open to tourism can offer services to the tourism sector for a long time [2, p. 47].

The topic of planning, which has made by various public organizations around the world, has created a number of competent authorities in this field. Numerous powers naturally create an atmosphere of ownerlessness and irresponsibility. The rise of environmental pollution in cities, mountains, forests, etc. to a level that affects negatively our lives is the result of confusion in planning. For this, there is a need for a consistent legal regulation for a certain system and period by ensuring coordination between the legal arrangements for the plans based on the settlement decisions. Instead of retail approaches that have a negative impact on the environment, sustainable planning should be carried out on the basis of integrated planning by creating a balance between the protection of the environment, the protection-use of natural, cultural and historical values.

Tourism and the environment are concepts that have much in common and symbolize their interaction with their common and collective sides. The environment is unique as a source of tourism. The existence of the environment is a condition for the existence of tourism and its survival. It is a well-known fact that tourism, which is developing against nature and the environment, will deprive itself of resources. A successful tourism needs a clean and well-arranged natural environment. Undoubtedly, the main principle when using

any natural resource should be to maintain a balance between the protection and use of those resources. This is a well-known fact and proven by scientific research that ecological problems and provocations resulting from the wasteful and inefficient use of natural resources have reached a point that threatens the lives of all living things in the world, including humans. Seeing that natural resources are becoming more and more depleted year by year is the main topic of the most serious discussions in all countries of the world, as well as scientific research and in terms of how today's people leave a natural environment for future generations [3, p. 171-172].

As a rule, tourism acts as a factor that stimulates the discovery, restoration and efficient use of natural resources and cultural-historical values. The reason is that the host country collects and tries to make full use of recreational resources to meet visitors with dignity, keep them as much as possible in its territory and above all, to create the best impression for potential tourists to come to the country through advertising. The second is that travelers are eager to look for and find something new, good and interesting during foreign tourist trips. The third is the possibility of using part of the income from tourism for the restoration and protection of national treasures [1, p. 89-90].

According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature, ecotourism is defined as travel and visits to areas that support entertainment, conscious conservation of natural and historical-cultural resources, have a low level of visitor benefits, benefit the local people socio-economically and preserve their initial natural purity. According to another explanation given by the Ecotourism Association, ecotourism can be characterized as a trip to nature, which protects the environment and the well-being of the local population. In other words, ecotourism also means protecting natural and cultural resources and opening them up to use of tourism. Taking this into account, tourism policy is based on three principles:

1. An efficient, effective and competitive development within this sector;
2. To create the most appropriate social environment for both foreign tourists and local people in accordance with universal values;
3. Preservation of the country's natural resources and enrichment of its cultural heritage.

A balance is maintained between economic, cultural and environmental goals at each stage of various tourism activities within the framework of these basic principles and trends [3, p. 72].

As a result of this approach, many countries have already certified natural and historical resources. This helps to guide the development of tourism and the protection of national treasures. In recent years, many countries have taken decisive measures (to try to neutralize the negative aspects of the rapidly developing foreign tourism to the maximum, as well as to create more favorable conditions for tourism, to protect and improve the natural and geographical environment) to implement nature protection measures, to create new national parks and reserves, to try to determine the limit of nature overload scientifically, etc. The greening of cities, the struggle against noise and ensuring cleanliness are the result of the requirements of tourism development to some extent [1, p. 90].

If the tourism sector, which has a number of economic, social and cultural benefits, is not properly controlled, environmental impacts can occur in the form of the destruction of natural areas, monuments of historical significance and coastal strips due to overuse of natural resources and the wrong choice of location. So, areas of natural life in the growing tourism sector have become modern resorts and the habitations of some exhausted species have become tourist bases and recreation areas in a growing tourism sector in some countries where tourism is developing [3, p. 172-173].

In this sense, the strengthening and restoration of forest protection in a number of European countries can be attributed to the services of international tourism. Besides its conservation function, tourism also gets significant income from natural resources. Including, the organization of excursions to caves has brought great benefits to many countries in recent years. Karst caves in Switzerland, France, the Czech Republic, Yugoslavia, Russia, Hungary and other countries attract tourists en masse. The rare “ornaments” of stalactites and stalagmites of these caves, which are of great importance for science, can be destroyed in the absence of special measures. Ensuring the interests of tourists and at the same time protecting the underground resources can be achieved only by investing in equipment and protection of cave nature [1, p. 90-91].

Some shortcomings are also encountered in the tourist areas of coastal countries, especially in the summer months, when solid waste is accumulated. Garbage often accumulates on the roadsides for a long time, so flies gather around it and the water that seeps out of the garbage gives off a foul smell. The means of municipalities to clean up landfills are very primitive and they are not sufficient. These tools and means are

very outdated in terms of modern technical equipment and are generally unsuitable for the gathering and disposal of solid waste. Therefore, it is not possible to transport these wastes far and dispose of them in accordance with environmental requirements [3, p.173].

Tourism has a negative impact on the natural resources of separate regions and districts, primarily intended for mass recreation and travel. The untouched, natural forest landscape is especially attractive for tourists. Forest fires caused by fires are mainly related to domestic tourism, not international tourism. Because, it is not intended to cook on bonfires on comfortable routes for foreign tourists. However, the creation of tourist complexes, which require the clearing of construction sites (usually in picturesque, green areas) by deforestation, is one of the factors creating the basis for the development of international tourism. National parks also attract tourists. No matter how kind the organizers and participants of the trips are to nature, the large number of visitors and the limited area of the national park cause the fauna to leave there and the plants to be trampled. Improving the communication system in the reserves, building a trade network and hotels to create high services for tourists and earn high incomes does not allow to preserve the landscape in its natural state. When there are no scientifically substantiated norms of acceptance of each reserve and they are not strictly observed, dangerous manifestations occur in the relationship between tourism and nature [1, p. 92-93].

Azerbaijan is a country with great potential for the development of the tourism sector. Recently, the expansion of the republic's foreign relations has given impetus to the development of recreation and tourism of Azerbaijan. Besides restoring the health and moral-psychological integrity of the population, this field also expands its employment, raises the sphere of social services and attracts more investment to the country.

The shores of the Caspian Sea are ideal in terms of tourism, recreation and relaxation and are distinguished by their unique features. Abundant sunny days, favorable dry climate, smooth coast, precious plains and foothill forests, fine sandy beaches, long summer season make it even more attractive. The beauty of natural purity of these places, which have unusually beautiful nature and climatic features, sea and river walks, therapeutic mud, interesting landscape samples, medicinal mineral waters, as well as conditions for the development of fishing or hunting various animals, creates favorable conditions for tourism.

Azerbaijan also has a feature of being a center of history and culture. More than 6000 natural, archeological, architectural and cultural monuments have been discovered in the country and these monuments are also protected by the state. Many of these date back to before Christ. There are unique architectural monuments in the Caspian zone, such as Gobustan rocks, Maiden Tower, Icheri Sheher complex, which are ancient human settlements. Besides caravanserais, mosques and museums, religious shrines are also factors that create the basis for the development of tourism in terms of historical and cultural significance. At the same time, the Azerbaijani people have a rich national tradition. Azerbaijan is also distinguished by its high culinary – cuisine culture.

The power of the mass media should be used to influence positively the development of tourism in Azerbaijan, which has unique natural beauties, and its becoming into one of the priority sectors of the country's economy. Unlike Azerbaijan, all countries spend large sums of money from their budgets to advertise and promote themselves [3, p. 175].

One of studies by WTO experts shows that the environment deteriorates rapidly, but is difficult to recover: despite the limited amount of environmental resources, tourists' "demand" for it is constantly increasing. High-quality environment is a kind of "raw material" for tourism. Therefore, besides the economical use of environmental resources, it is necessary to ensure its protection. Besides taking care of the environment, it should be taken into account that a declining environment will inevitably harm both tourism and the economic development of the region. Therefore, the interest of all sections of society in the development of tourism and at the same time protection of national resources, high speed and economic efficiency of domestic and international tourism, the steady development of productive forces and the people's welfare allow to solve the abovementioned issues successfully [1, p. 95].

Conclusion. The need for tourism to be a user of nature and cultural heritage, as well as a protector and creator of this heritage is one of the main priorities of international documents. Because tourism resources are the common wealth of mankind. People living in the area have special rights and proper responsibilities in relation to tourism resources. Such an approach is reflected in the "Global Code of Ethics for Tourism". This document states: "Introduced tourism policy and tourism activities should be carried out in order to respect the cultural, archaeological and literary

heritage and preserve it for future generations. Special attention should be paid to monuments, archeological excavations and historical sites that are open for tourism use. Access of privately owned cultural heritage sites, collections, museums and monuments to tourists should be supported. At least part of the income from trips by tourists to cultural facilities should be spent on the protection, restoration and expansion of these facilities. Tourism activities should be aimed at the protection and dissemination of cultural traditions and the standardization of culture should not be allowed at all”.

As a result of such an approach at the international level, tourism that creates interest in the culture, traditions and way of life of peoples in the modern world and invites people to live in mutual understanding is considered one of the most important areas of interest in maintaining peace. Positive changes in speed, comfort, power, capacity, opportunity and price in the communication-information means are important factors in the democratization of travel. All these changes show that the future of tourism will be brighter. However, despite such developments, terrorism, regional and local conflicts, wars, as well as natural disasters are the most important enemies of the tourism sector. Because, as we know, the development of tourism in the region depends primarily on political stability, peace and tranquility, as well as security of the region. That is why the civilized world supports intercultural dialogue, cultural integration and supports the protection of cultural diversity. The care for the historical-cultural heritage of mankind and the riches of nature is behind the strict control of cultural factors in the tourism sector. The growth of such a trend gives reason to be optimistic not only about the prospects of tourism, but also about the future of the world in general.

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MƏDƏNİ TURİZMDƏ ƏTRAF MÜHİTİN VƏ TƏBİİ İRSİN QORUNMASI PROBLEMLƏRİ

İqtisadi, sosial və mədəni faydası olan turizm sektoruna yaxşı nəzarət edilmədikdə, təbii sərvətlərin ifrat istifadəsi və yanlış yer seçimləri səbəbindən təbii sahələrin, tarixi dəyərlərin və sahilyanı yerlərin dağıdılması kimi ətraf mühitə mənfi təsirləri ola bilər. Həmçinin ölkəmizdə getdikcə böyüyən turizm sektorunda təbii həyat sahələri modern tətillə şəhərciklərinə, təhlükə altındakı dəniz bağları, qumsallıqları da turistik təsisatlara döndərilmişdir.

Hələ də milli və ya regional olaraq ekoturizm düşüncəsinin olmaması səbəbindən çirkin və nəzarətsiz strukturlar artır, yabani təbiətdən sui-istifadə edilir, flora və faunanı tanınmadan və bölgənin imkanlarını bilinmədən turlar təşkil edilir. Təşkil edilən turlarda hər nə qədər düzənli və ətraf mühitə ehtiyatlı münasibətdən danışılsa da, plansız, nəzarətsiz və bölgənin tutum imkanları öyrənilmədən həyata keçirilən bu turizmin ekoturizm olmayacağı bir həqiqətdir.

Açar sözlər: təbii sərvətlər, meşə landşaftı, mədəni turizm, turist obyektləri, ətraf mühit.

Сиявущ Магишов (Азербайджан)

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ОХРАНЫ ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ И ПРИРОДНОГО НАСЛЕДИЯ В КУЛЬТУРНОМ ТУРИЗМЕ

Слабый контроль над сектором туризма, имеющим экономические, социальные и культурные преимущества, чрезмерное использование

природных ресурсов и неправильный выбор местоположения могут иметь негативные последствия для окружающей среды, такие как разрушение природных территорий, исторических ценностей и прибрежных территорий. Кроме того, природные зоны жизни были превращены в современные курортные поселки, исчезающие дачи и пляжи были превращены в туристические объекты в растущем секторе туризма в нашей стране.

Разрастаются уродливые и неконтролируемые сооружения, жестоко обращаются с дикой природой, а туры организуются без учета флоры и фауны и без знания потенциала региона из-за отсутствия национального или регионального экотуристического мышления. Какими бы организованными и экологичными ни были туры, фактом является то, что этот туризм, осуществляемый без плана, без контроля и без изучения возможностей региона, экотуризмом не станет.

Ключевые слова: природные ресурсы, лесной ландшафт, культурно-познавательный туризм, туристские объекты, окружающая среда.